

Appraisal Of State Response To Terrorism And Insurgency In Nigeria: Boko-Haram In North-East Experience.

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Abstract

The security of lives and properties remains a fundamental and constitutional responsibility of the state. This has however taken a different dimension in recent years, following the upsurge of terrorism and insurgency in the Northeast of Nigeria and beyond. The attacks on Nigerians particularly, the people in the Northeast by the Islamist Sect called Boko Haram, has continued to wreck havocs on the security and peaceful coexistence of the various tribes and culture that constitute the Nigeria body polity. To this end, this paper examined state response to terrorism and insurgency in the North-east of Nigeria and how it has affected development in the region. The study adopted the secondary method of data collection, derived from Journals, Textbooks, Mimeographs, Newspapers, and Publications by Governmental and Non-Governmental institutions. Findings revealed the impact of state response to the activities of Bokoharam insurgency and terrorism in Nigeria. Its socio-economic and political effect such as, the closure of businesses and the non-conduct of elections in some parts of the areas affected amongst others. furthermore, the study recommends some ways to mitigated, through proper collaboration with the relevant security apparatuses. It also canvassed the need for government to ensure justice and equity in the handling of state affairs at all times, to avoid feelings of deprivation and inequality in the system. Finally, the study highlighted the over haul of some of the intelligence and information-sharing and communication strategies as a veritable tool for fighting the upsurge of Boko-Haram Sects in Nigeria.

Keywords: Terrorism, Insurgency, State, Boko-Haram, Insecurity

Introduction:

A fundamental responsibility of the state as embedded in section 14, sub section 2, part B, of the constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (1999) is the security of the life and property of its citizens. Other responsibilities include the protection of its territoriality; sovereignty; guaranteeing its socio-economic and political stability etc. This threat has further been propelled by the emergence and rise of "Violent Non-State Actors" (VNSAs) according to Adesoji, (2014), argues that the process of globalization has further given advantage to the terrorists to carry out their nefarious and dangerous attacks on citizens, institutions and critical infrastructure of the state. Terrorism and its negative consequences date back to the pre-historic time otherwise referred to the period antiquity. Adetula (2011), argues that prevalence and escalation have been accentuated in the twenty-first century especially since the September 11, 2001 bombing of the World Trade Centre (WTC) in the United States by the Al-Qaeda terrorist network led by Osama Bin Laden. That attack has been followed by many similar attacks in Africa, Asia, Europe, and other parts of the world. The ugly incidence of Boko Haram in the submission of Adesoji, (2014), came as a result of factors such as religiously motivated crisis, proliferation of weapons of war, social and political injustice, corruption, unemployment, poverty, weak institutional structure, economic marginalization, lack of political will etc.

However, terrorism-related violence dates back to the late 1990s. On August 7, 1998, two massive bombs simultaneously exploded outside the United States embassies in Dares Salaam in Tanzania and Nairobi in Kenya, killing 224 people and injuring 5,000 others. Responsibility was quickly traced to Al-Qaeda. Four years afterwards, Al-Qaeda operatives struck again, killing 15 people in an Israeli-owned hotel near Mombasa in Kenya, and simultaneously fired missiles at an Israeli passenger jet taking off from Mombasa airport (Gabriel, 2018). However, since September 11, 2001, the Continent has experienced significant increase in planned and actual attacks by terrorist networks (Adelusi, 2011). Weak domestic security, governance failure, post-election violence, corruption, religious intolerance, porous borders, proliferation of weapons from destabilized countries in the aftermath of the Arab Spring and globalization have provided terrorist groups chapter four the leeway to carry out audacious attacks in Africa including Nigeria (Onuoha, 2012).. Blair (2015), identified Angola, Burundi, Central African Republic; Cote d'Ivoire, Ethiopia and Uganda as being at risk of increased terrorism due to the presence of the following four factors – extrajudicial killing, lack of women's political rights, lack of intergroup cohesion and political instability. As Alexander, (2018) would say, Boko Haram represents an ugly paradox: Its ideas have limited appeal which is significantly concerned about power, hence government purposeful and proactive response becomes a key factor to the survival of the Nigerian state.

There is no gainsaying the fact that several studies on terrorism and insurgency in relations to Boko Haram as in the case Sanda, (2014), Osita, (2019), Thomas, (2016) and other notable scholars. Interestingly, in all of the studies and literatures consulted, none of them looked deeply from perspective of state responses to terrorism and insurgency in the Northeast, Nigeria, hence this work is out to fill some gap in knowledge and equally add to existing body of knowledge. Some other puzzles the work is set to ascertain the degree of damage done by the sects their network and strategies which has taken a global dimension and the overall challenge it poses to the nation and by extension, the world. This study amongst others examined state responses to terrorism and insurgency in the northeast of Nigeria. This is considered significant because its outcome would be of immense benefit and assistance to the Nigerian state, security apparatuses, and international community in the formulation of relevant

anti-terrorism legislations and policies in their efforts to contend with the challenges of terrorism.

Terrorism

The concept of terrorism is not a new phenomenon in human history, especially in Nigeria. The term terrorism from the etymological concept had its origin from the French word 'terrorism' which in turn was derived from the Latin word, 'terreo' which means to frighten or give a threat. It is a concept that is complex, multifaceted and emotive. It is complex because it combines so many different aspects of human experiences, including politics, psychology, philosophy, military strategy, religion and history. Obi (2011); Ekanem; Dada and Ejue (2012) define terrorism as the use of unlawful, illegal and violent means by small group of people to achieve their selfish aim. Terrorism is emotive because experiences of terrorist acts arouse tremendous feelings and because those who see terrorists as justified often have strong feelings concerning the rightness of the use of violence in resolving differences among Mankind. In many cases terrorists internationally choose to attack innocent targets, to make their political or religious demands from the government or people with which they are in conflict, violating domestic and international laws. Ogirai, (2015) described terrorism as the use of threat or anxiety-induced extra normal violence for political purpose by any individual or group whether acting for or in a position to establish governmental authority where such action is intended to influence the attitudes and behaviour of a largest group wider than the immediate victims and through the nationality or foreign ties and its perpetrators. In the opinion of (Ekanem 2012, Juergensmeyer 2003), terrorism is a tool used to achieve a specific outcome by using force or violence on one segment of society with the primary goal of causing fear in the larger society to make change in that society. Terrorism is a form of violent conflict which is a form of unconventional warfare.

Terrorism includes a range of social and political problems whose behavioural scope is boundless and includes behaviour that appears to be abnormal. Friedlander, (2017) in his opinion argued that terrorism is often characterized by the use of violence against civilians, with the expressed desire of causing terror or panic in the population. At the individual level, some experts have distinguished rational, psychological, and cultural origins of terrorism (Simonsen & Jeremy 2000). Scholars such as Barkan and Snowkan (1986), also looked at the inherent nature and violence in humans contributes to the fast spreading rate of terrorism and insurgency as an inherent phenomenon. Terrorism in Nigeria in whichever dimension is often stimulated by economic considerations. For instance, the Niger Delta agitations were greatly underpinned by the bid of what (Ake, 1981) referred to as the primary material condition Obi (2011); Ekanem; Dada and Ejue (2012) define terrorism as the use of unlawful, illegal and violent means by small group of people to achieve their selfish aim. Terrorism is emotive because experiences of terrorist acts arouse tremendous feelings and because those who see terrorists as justified often have strong feelings concerning the rightness of the use of violence in resolving differences among Mankind.

Insurgency

Insurgency is characterized by some common strings: political, psychological, coercive, dynamic and deliberate. Its ideologies and activities is caused by human injustice, perceived oppression or man's inhumanity to man, marginalization, exploitation, greed, deprivation,

poverty, corruption, oppression, and repression. The United States Federal Bureau of Investigation (FBI) as contained in Madunagu, (2007) described the act of insurgency as the unlawful use of violence against persons or property to intimidate or coerce a government, the civilian population or any segment thereof, in furtherance of social objective or frivolous reasons. The phenomenon of insurgency has been widely examined in the extant literature, yet there is no universally accepted definition. This act of insurgency also conveys terrorism impressions which are often viewed from different perspectives. Ogirai, (2015) described Insurgency as the use of threat or anxiety-induced extra normal violence for political purpose by any individual or group whether acting for or in a position to establish governmental authority where such action is intended to influence the attitudes and behaviour of a largest group wider than the immediate victims and through the nationality or foreign ties and its perpetrators. In the opinion of Ekanem (2012), terrorism is an “acts by non-state actors involving the threatened or actual use of illegal force or violence to attain a political, economic, religious, or social goal through fear, coercion, or intimidation as witnessed in Nigeria during the reprobate regime of General Sani Abacha between 1995 – 1998 when bombs were used as a terror weapon against Nigerians. In a world perceived as peaceful, an act of political violence may be considered as domestic terrorism, while the same act of violence can be considered justified by others who perceive the world to be at war. The United States Federal Bureau of Investigation (FBI) as contained in Madunagu, (2007) described terrorism as the unlawful use of force or violence against persons or property to intimidate or coerce a government, the civilian population or any segment thereof, in furtherance of political or social objective. Friedlander, (2017) in his contributions argued that the victims or objects of a terrorist attack have little intrinsic value to the terrorist but represent a larger human audience whose reaction the terrorists seek.

Theoretical Framework of Analysis

Morrison (1971) argued that a lot of theories exist for providing explanation to acts of terrorism and insurgency. The paper adopted the structural theory of revolutionary otherwise known as transformational theory which was developed by an economist and sociologists to explain the process of economic development and society. Rostow, Chinney and Hirschman were the main advocates and the relative deprivation theory by both Garry Runciman and Ted Gurr in providing explanations to state response to terrorism and insurgency in the North East Nigeria. The theory tends to explain the problem associated in counter-insurgency efforts and the war against terrorism and how states can adapt faster and take over the enemy's own shifting tactics and innovations. Applying structural theory in the context of terrorism and insurgency, Barkan and Snowden (1986) observed that, Structural theories of revolution emphasize that weaknesses in state structures encourage the potential for revolution and a fragile system which by extension may lead to insecurity and terrorism. (Deleuze, 2002). This theory is relevant to this discourse because it offers important suggestions for the fight against terrorism and insurgency to insure internal and international security.

The theory of relative deprivation became relevant to the study because, rather than examine the causes of a given situation alone, relative deprivation theory is interested in the genesis of the problem in either individual or social structures. Relative deprivation seeks to explain the process and emotion of crime, the fluidity of deviant activity and as such, connects to the contemporary issues. Deprivation should therefore be understood from the offenders' inner feelings because not all poor people criminals or may have the huge to commit crime. The central idea of relative deprivation theory suggests that individuals or groups feel deprived

when their current circumstances are negatively compared to the situation of others. In sociology, relative deprivation theory is a view of social change and movements according to which people take action for social change in order to acquire something (for example, opportunities, status and wealth) that others possess and which they believe they should have too.

Operational Differences Between Insurgency and Terrorism

The distinction between terrorism and insurgency according Pape, (2005), is not merely theoretical as the appropriate responses to the two phenomena are very different. Before addressing preferred strategies to counter each, one should establish how they are alike and how they differ. Unfortunately, existing definitions do more to cloud than clarify the issues. Neither academic nor government experts agreed on a suitable definition for terrorism. Operationally, there is no clear cut difference between the goals of terrorist and insurgent groups and insurgencies, but certain characteristics might reflect distinctions. Despite, these allusions, certain differences still exist according to (Silke, 2011).

Dichotomy between Insurgency and Terrorism

S/N	TERRORISM	INSURGENCY
1	Terrorism is indiscriminate	Insurgency on the other hand is based on the selective use of violence against a people who do not comply politically with the wishes of the rebels or the government
2.	Terrorism may pursue political or even revolutionary goals but their violence replaces rather than c complements a political program	Insurgency combines violence with political programs in pursuit of revolutionary purposes in a way that terrorism cannot duplicate
3	Terrorist units are usually smaller and comprised of isolated teams not organized into formal military chain of command	Insurgency are usually in large number with identifiable purposes and reasons of operations
4	Terrorism is considered to be a method of pursuing political goal.	Insurgency is a political movement aimed at realizing a specific political goa
5	Terrorism relies on public impact, and is therefore conscious of the advantage of avoiding the negative connotations of the term "terrorists" in identifying themselves A terror group does not require and rarely has the active support or even the sympathy of a large fraction of the population.	Insurgents will frequently describe themselves as "insurgents" or "guerillas", terrorists will not refer to themselves as "terrorists" but describe it using military or political terminology ("freedom fighters", "soldiers", "activists"). The ultimate goal of an insurgency is to challenge the existing government for control of all or a portion of its territory, or force political concessions in sharing political power.

6	Terrorism does not attempt to challenge government forces directly, but acts to change perceptions as to the effectiveness or legitimacy of the government itself.	Insurgency need not require the targeting of non-combatants, although many insurgencies expand the accepted legal definition of combatants to include police and security personnel in addition to the military
7	Terrorists are by definition conducting crimes under both civil and military legal codes. Terrorists routinely claim that were they to adhere to any "law of war" or accept any constraints on the scope of their violence, it would place them at a disadvantage vis-vis the establishment	Ultimately, the difference between insurgency and terrorism comes down to the intent of the actor. Insurgency movements and guerilla forces can adhere to international norms regarding the law of war in achieving their goals
8	One common characteristic of all insurgencies is their significant material inferiority to the counterinsurgent, at least in the early stages of the conflict.	One common characteristic of all terrorism is their significant material superior to the counterinsurgent.
9	External support, recognition or approval from other countries or political entities can be useful to insurgents, but is not required	Insurgencies require the active or tacit support of some portion of the population involved

Compiled by the researcher

Terrorists and Insurgents' Tactics and Weapons of Carrying out Attacks of the People

According to Walter, (1976), warfare comprises not just the encounter of individual soldiers, but (more importantly), a pattern of tactics and strategy in relationship to the opposing forces taken as a whole. Some of the tactics deployed by terrorists and insurgents as identified by Marighella (2002), are:

- i. **Propaganda:** Propaganda has proved to be a seminal weapon in the battle for hearts and minds. Successful insurgents use communication media to construct and disseminate information in a way that manages the relevant audiences' opinion and behaviour in their favour (Marighella, 2002). According to Mao Tse-Tung (1963), Propaganda is an instrument that tends to favour the insurgent over the ruling power. In contrast, the insurgent group free from such responsibility enjoys greater creative freedom when formulating its revolutionary propagandistic messages.
- ii. **Guerrilla Tactics:** This is a major approach based on intelligence, ambush, deception, sabotage and espionage, undermining an authority through long, low-intensity confrontation. It can be quite successful against an unpopular foreign or local regime as demonstrated by the Cuban revolution, Afghanistan War and Vietnam War. According to Times (2013), it is a major tactics used by the insurgent groups in actualizing their nefarious activities in society.
- iii. **Agitation:** Often grouped together with propaganda as agitprop, agitation is the use of agitators to stir up discontent both real and imagined with the regime and propose a

course of action to right these perceived wrongs. The traditional targets of agitators have been the shop floor, students' unions and the junior officers' mess halls of the military. These tactics are useful

- iv. **Assassinations:** Insurgent groups have often employed assassination as a tool to further their course. Assassinations provide several functions for such groups, namely the removal of specific enemies and as propaganda tools to focus the attention of media and politics on their course. These tactics were used during the Irish Republican Army guerrilla of 1919-1921 which killed many police intelligence officers during the Irish war of independence.
- v. **Rebellion:** Insurgencies are movements to overthrow governments. The United States was founded by an insurgency, when the colonies fought England for independence. In the Star Wars movies, the rebel forces stage an insurgency. Around the world, many insurgencies exist, using violent and other means.
- vi. **Deception:** Insurgency employs a deception primarily for purposes of infiltration prior to an attack. This technique allows Boko Haram fighters to position themselves inside a village prior to an attack. On 14 February 2014, Boko Haram fighters exploited the hope that the Nigerian military would answer repeated calls to send soldiers to protect the village of Izghe in Borno State. 61 Boko Haram used a similar technique when they kidnapped the Chibok girls, as noted previously (Marighella, 2002).

Insecurity Situation and Boko-Haram's and its Effects in Nigeria

Boko Haram insurgency could thus link to perceived discrepancy between the preferred way of life (to maintain the sanctity of orthodox Islam) and the actual state of their existence (secular state) that influence the dissonance. Prominently, it should be noted that the voice of few elements that initially reacted to the perceived dissonance is what the issue at stake requires in order to gain popular support and to a large extent, the personal dissonance grows to become group level grievances and discontentment. As a consequence, it transcends from a micro to macro level spectacle. Fundamentally, the crucial target of Boko Haram is to destabilize Nigeria, beginning with the northeast therefore make it ungovernable as this could lead to a situation of break-up of the country or imposition of Islamic ways of life.

The relevance of cognitive dissonance theory to this study is that, it reflects meaningful philosophy behind the existentiality of Boko Haram sect and to a large extent explains government inability to tame the challenges posed by the sect. Since then, the group has demonstrated remarkable adaptability, employing various tactics and methods to further its agenda. Notably, the movement has expanded into neighboring countries Cameroon, Chad, and Niger (see map below) and has also demonstrated its capacity to seize and hold towns and villages, particularly during the height of its insurgency between 2014 and 2015.

The situation has caused a lot of setback in various aspects of the nation's economy. On the education sub-sector for example, data gathered through secondary sources such as, textbooks, journals, media, unpublished work, government reports and Non-government reports showed the magnitude of impact/damage done to the sub-sector as a result of the activities of the terrorist and insult groups. The sector suffered a huge setback as government was forced to close down Schools and Colleges. This according to Chris, (2012) led the Nigeria government

to effectively collaborate with the United State government and the international community in the training of over 30.000 troops since it started in 2015 to help secure schools in the region.

- i. **Effect on education:** The paper revealed the various ways Boko Haram insurgency and terrorism has affected Education in the Northeast region in Nigeria. One major sector that has suffered severe setback as a result of Boko Haram activities in the North East of Nigeria is the education sub-sector. During the period under study, Schools, Colleges, teachers and students formed the main targets and they all suffered immense damages. Schools were totally closed down by government for fear of possible attacks like in the case of the Chibok girls where over 230 school children were abducted with no trace of location. This according to Hassan, (2014) caused a lot of damaged to the already educational backward region in terms of education, hence adequate attention according to Omorogbe, (2019) suggested the need for government to be proactive and not reactive.
- ii. **Effect on social activities:** As earlier indicated in this study coupled with the data in the table above, Boko Haram has had a serious impact on socio-economic activities not only in the affected areas but the entire country. Findings further showed that beyond religious, political and Psychological reasons other sub-sectors such as the social sector have equally been negatively affected. The phenomenon of internally displaced Persons has become a social problem and dangerous to economic development. The population of IDPs in the North is alarming because many of them are family men and women who ordinarily are supposed to fend for their family.
- iii. **Its Effect on political activities:** One other major areas that was drastically affected by Boko Haram activities is political activities. As a result of the intense insurgent activities, the study revealed that most persons who ought to participate in elections were disenfranchised. Investigation revealed that in Borno state for example, INEC Resident Electoral Commissioner, Muhammed Ibrahim provided the voting details at an interactive session organized by the Nigeria Union of Journalists (NUJ) for election officials, civil society organizations, political parties and journalists. It was gathered that out of the Twenty-Seven local government areas in the North East of Nigeria, only eight of them could hold elections due to Boko Haram activities in 2009.
- iv. **Psychological Effect:** The psychological implication of Boko Haram activities cannot be over emphasized. A lot of lives and properties have been claimed by the sect with huge injuries inflicted on thousands of people. Studies emanating from the University of Port Harcourt have shown that aside the physical disability which those who survived violent crimes and warfare sustained, psychiatric disorder is rife and manifest. The number of houses that have been destroyed by the sect since inception as revealed in the study in alarming.
- v. **Economic Effect:** One significant factor that has stimulated the drive towards violent extremism, recruitment and support for Boko Haram as revealed above is economic deprivation. Abject poverty and economic dislocation of livestock have drastically reduced the option of many young Nigerians in the northern region. As highlighted above, deducing from the structural violence paradigms, individual and group grievances, such as poverty, unemployment, illiteracy, discrimination, and economic marginalization, was identified as been used as a mobilizing by sinister groups as observed in the study to find support and recruits for terrorists' violence.

Impediments to Effective Response to Terrorism and Insurgency in the Northeast of Nigeria

The impediment to state and government in the fight against Boko Haram according to findings gathered from the various sources and as witnessed in some of the literatures captured above. The investigation identified six impediments confronting an effective fight against Boko Haram and insurgency as argued by Mohammed (2024) in the Northeast of Nigeria are as follows:

- i. Crisis of multifarious illegal roots around the Nigeria borders
- ii. Government inability to address the root cause serves as a major impediment
- iii. The endemic poverty in parts of the region which makes it very easy for the insurgents to recruit new members
- iv. Problem of weaponry. Study also identified the lack of sophisticated weapons in engaging the insurgents as a major impediment
- v. Corruption. Money voted to educate people or bolster campaign against Boko Haram end up in official pockets and private hands
- vi. Boko Haram huge collaborating network and influence and poor military strategy were also identified in this study as a major factor

Records available to the Nigeria Immigration Service (NIS) according to Ogunlesi, (2015) revealed that there are over 1.400 illegal routs into Nigeria, 1316 more than the approved border control posts. This fact supports the reasons adduced in the study that is causing intensed insecurity in the Northeast of Nigeria. This fact agrees with Mayer, (2012) which posited that fighting terrorism would be difficult if the affected state is affected with porous boundary issues and without adequate formulas to deal with the situation. This finding supports findings and observations in other studies and literature. According to Odita and Akan (2014), in economic terms, what the Boko Haram insurrection created is a systemic distortion of existing economic patterns and structure in northern Nigeria. They further noted, Nigeria's northern region which has 78% of the country's land mass is the backbone of Nigeria's agricultural production in food and cash crops as well as livestock. argued that Boko Haram insurgency has affected agriculture especially in some of the country's main food-growing areas (Yobe, Adamawa and Borno states) worst hit by the insurgency, farmers are afraid to go to their farms as a result of fear of being attacked.

Conclusion

Conclusively, in recent times, Nigeria has emerged as a terrorism country in the eyes of the international community according to Nigeria Human Right Watch (2010, 2014). The growing rate of insecurity and the onslaught of terrorists' activities against the system particularly in the North, and other growing Muslim fundamentalist elements emerging in North of Nigeria does not only poses security concerns for the country and the international community, but are themselves huge symptoms of state weakness and possible failure. The inability of the Nigerian state to respond adequately to nipping the phenomenon of terrorism in the bud as observed in most literatures extracted, poses serious danger to the country's nascent democracy and economic development. There is no escaping the fact that terrorist attacks in Nigeria and globally have almost exclusively taking an escalating approach.

Recommendations

At the end of the investigation, the paper presented its recommendations as follows:

- i. That following the identified gaps identified in the area of collaboration among countries, Nigeria Government should involve a new mechanism geared towards combating terrorists' activities effective collaboration.
- ii. Budgetary provisions should be made for the acquisition of superior arms and weapons for effective counterterrorism operations.
- iii. That there is the need for steady information and intelligence sharing and communication amongst stakeholders and the general public on the need to be security conscious.
- iv. Nigeria government should put mechanism in place that will help arrest and control the influx of illegal immigrants and weapons into the country
- v. It also canvassed the need for government to ensure justice and equity in the handling of state affairs
- vi. Finally, there should be a deliberate effort by government to eliminate discrimination, nepotism, hunger, unemployment, inequality and all manner of deprivations inherent in the system.

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